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SUPPORTING INFORMATION

DRomics: a turnkey tool to support the use of the dose-response framework for omics data in ecological risk assessment

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S1) MATERIAL AND METHODS

*This section introduces the methods used to design the microarray and to assess the transcriptomics response of the chlorophyte *Scenedesmus vacuolatus*.*

Microarray design

As no commercial microarray was available for *S. vacuolatus* a microarray was designed based on a former RNA sequencing experiment. In brief, synchronized cultures of the chlorophyte were challenged by 18 treatments of different stressors such as chemicals, high ionic concentrations, heat and nutrient deficiencies. Algae from these treatments were harvested at different steps of the cell cycle by centrifugation (22°C, 10 min, 3300 g). Total RNA was isolated from algal pellets using Trizol (Invitrogen Carlsbad, CA) according to the manufacturer's instruction with minor modifications. Quality and quantity of the extracted RNA were analysed by a Nanodrop Spectrophotometer (ND-1000, Peqlab, Erlangen, Germany) and an Experion™ RNA Highsens Analysis Kit (BioRad). mRNA was isolated from total RNA extracts using the Dynabeads® mRNA purification kit (ThermoFischer, Germany) according to the manufacturer's instructions resulting in 1.9 µg L⁻¹ pooled mRNA from all exposure conditions. Preparation of cDNA library was conducted according to the manufacturer's instruction of the Roche 454 GS-FLX Titanium platform. Briefly, 0.5 µg pooled mRNA was converted to double-stranded cDNA using a cDNA synthesis system Kit and a cDNA Rapid Library Prep Kit (Roche) and sequenced afterwards using the Roche 454 GS-FLX Titanium platform. The sequencing resulted in 934,866 reads with a length of up to 400 bps. 97% of the reads could be assembled into 22,000 contigs using Newbler software¹. Out of this data set 21,495 contigs were selected to design a 8X60 K microarray using eArray (Agilent Technologies, Böblingen, Germany). Remaining gaps on the array were filled randomly with already represented probes. The probes sequences and the related contigs are presented in an excel file. Genome information (cDNA sequences) have been deposited in NCBI's Sequence Read Archive and are accessible through the SRA accession number PRJNA498405 (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/sra/PRJNA498405>).

S. vacuolatus exposure to triclosan and RNA extraction

Synchronized cultures of the chlorophyte *S. vacuolatus* (Shih. et Krauss strain 211-15, culture collection Pringsheim (SAG Göttingen, Germany)) were grown in a sterile inorganic medium (pH 6.4) at 28°C by using a 14:10 h light:dark cycle². Chlorophytes were exposed for 14 hours to seven concentrations (0.69, 1.22, 2.15, 3.77, 6.63, 11.65, 20.47 µg/L) of triclosan (CalbioChem, Germany, CAS: 3380-34-5, purity of 99.8 %) and one solvent control (final DMSO concentration of 0.1 %) for 5 replicates in 500mL flasks containing 10⁶ cells/mL. Concentrations were chosen according to pre-studies, using 7 concentrations of

triclosan in the range of 0.69 – 20.5 µg/L covering a full concentration response curve from no inhibition to 100% inhibition of algal growth and revealing an EC₅₀ of 6.6 µg/L. Additionally, the quality of exposure conditions was analysed revealing a recovery of triclosan in the media of 81% during the exposure duration of 14h. With a focus on mode-of-action-related responses in the transcriptome at low concentrations we chose an exposure range below the EC₅₀ value, hence the two highest exposure concentrations (11.65 and 20.47 µg/L) were not considered for the transcriptome analysis.

Two times 80 mL suspensions of triclosan-exposed cultures were then harvested by centrifugation (22°C, 10 min, 3300 g). Culture pellets were resuspended in 500µL TRIZOL and stored at -80°C until further analysis. After cell lysis and RNA extraction using a FastPrep®24 homogenizer system (Biomedicals, Santa Ana, USA) and Phase Lock™ Gele Tubes (5 Prime GmbH, Hamburg, Germany), total RNA was further purified using a RNeasy®Plant Mini Kit (Quiagen, Hilden, Germany) according to the manufacturer's instructions. RNA quantity and quality were analyzed using a NanoDrop Spectrophotometer (ND-1000, Peqlab, Erlangen, Germany) revealing an absorption coefficient of 260/280 nm of 1.9 on average, which is within the quality criteria for purity of extracted RNA of 1.8-2.1 requested by the manufacturer.

Microarray analysis

In total, 40 microarrays were used in this study. The microarrays were disposed on 5 slides, meaning that each slide was composed of 8 microarrays (Figure S1). On each slide, each microarray was associated to one of the different treatments (from the control to the highest concentration tested). Thus, each slide represented one replicate.

Fifty ng of purified RNA were labeled using the Low Input Quick Amp Labeling Kit, one color (Agilent Technologies). Finally 40 µL cy3-labeled fragmented cRNA per sample were hybridized to each microarray for 17h at 65°C. Then, the 40 microarrays were washed and scanned, using an Agilent DNA Microarray scanner. Fluorescence intensities were extracted using the Agilent Feature Extraction software. One of the criteria used to assess the quality of microarray analysis was based on the spot finding at the four corners of the arrays (on image per array=40 images) and the Agilent SpikeIns concentration-response. Quality criteria were satisfying for each array (Table S1). The fluorescence data have been deposited in NCBI's Gene Expression Omnibus³ and are accessible via GEO Series accession number GSE122159 (<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/geo/query/acc.cgi?acc=GSE122159>).

Figure S1: Microarray experimental design.

Table S1. Quality control metrics related to each microarray included in the tool development (=without 2.2 and 2.3, the two highest concentrations). For array numbers, 1.1: concentration 1; 1.2: concentration 2; 1.3: concentration 3; 1.4: concentration 4; 2.1: concentration 5, 2.4: control).

Slide	Array	Aligned to grid	SpikeIns Slope	SpikeIns R ²
1	1.1	1	1.08	1
	1.2	1	1.05	0.99
	1.3	1	1.07	1
	1.4	1	1.07	0.99
	2.1	1	1.08	1
	2.4	1	1.1	0.99
2	1.1	1	1.07	0.99
	1.2	1	1.08	1
	1.3	1	1.08	1
	1.4	1	1.05	0.99
	2.1	1	1.09	0.99
	2.4	1	1.05	0.99
3	1.1	1	1.09	1
	1.2	1	1.07	0.99
	1.3	1	1.05	0.99
	1.4	1	1.06	1
	2.1	1	1.07	0.99
	2.4	1	1.09	0.99
4	1.1	1	1.08	1
	1.2	1	1.04	1
	1.3	1	1.08	1
	1.4	1	1.06	1
	2.1	1	1.08	1
	2.4	1	1.06	1
5	1.1	1	1.05	0.99
	1.2	1	1.06	0.99
	1.3	1	1.04	0.99
	1.4	1	1.06	1
	2.1	1	1.07	1
	2.4	1	1.08	1

S2) COMPARISON OF INTER-ARRAY NORMALIZATION METHODS

Here, are presented the graphical outputs (also provided in the DRomics tool) of the normalization step for each proposed method.

Figure S2. Boxplots of fluorescence values (in log₂) for each array, before and after normalization by each proposed method.

S3) DESCRIPTION OF THE BIPHASIC MODELS

Description of the 5-parameter Gauss-probit and log-Gauss-probit models.

The 5-parameter Gauss-probit model is defined as the sum of a Gauss part and a probit part as illustrated in Figure S3:

$$y = f \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \times \left(\frac{x-e}{b}\right)^2\right) + d + (c-d) \Phi\left(\frac{x-e}{b}\right)$$

See also Table 1 of the manuscript for parameter description.

From this formulation one can calculate its first derivative as below:

$$\begin{aligned} y' &= f \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \times \left(\frac{x-e}{b}\right)^2\right) \times \left(-\frac{1}{2} \times \frac{2(x-e)}{b^2}\right) + \frac{(c-d)}{b\sqrt{2\pi}} \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \times \left(\frac{x-e}{b}\right)^2\right) \\ &= \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \times \left(\frac{x-e}{b}\right)^2\right) \left(\frac{-f \times (x-e)}{b^2} + \frac{(c-d)}{b\sqrt{2\pi}}\right) \\ &= \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \times \left(\frac{x-e}{b}\right)^2\right) \left(\frac{-\sqrt{2\pi} \times f \times (x-e) + b \times (c-d)}{b^2 \sqrt{2\pi}}\right) \end{aligned}$$

This derivative is null for a unique value of x :

$$x = e + \frac{b(c-d)}{f\sqrt{2\pi}}.$$

The Gauss-probit model thus describes a biphasic model if $f \neq 0$, with the maximum (if $f > 0$) or the minimum (if $f < 0$) reached at $x = e + \frac{b(c-d)}{f\sqrt{2\pi}}$.

The log-Gauss-probit model is the same model in log-scale, obtained by replacing x by $\ln(x)$ and e by $\ln(e)$:

$$y = f \exp\left(-\frac{1}{2} \times \left(\frac{\ln(x) - \ln(e)}{b}\right)^2\right) + d + (c-d) \Phi\left(\frac{\ln(x) - \ln(e)}{b}\right)$$

It is thus also a biphasic model if $f \neq 0$, with the maximum (if $f > 0$) or the minimum (if $f < 0$) reached at $\ln(x) = \ln(e) + \frac{b(c-d)}{f\sqrt{2\pi}}$, so at $x = e \times \exp\left(\frac{b(c-d)}{f\sqrt{2\pi}}\right)$.

Figure S3. Schematic description of the 5-parameter Gauss-Probit model, as an addition of a Gaussian part and a probit part, with realistic values of parameters (such as some encountered in our data sets): $b = 1.5$, $c = 3$, $d = 6$, $e = 3$, $f = 2$.

S4) MODELLING COMPLEMENTARY RESULTS

This part presents complementary results for the modelling step: examples of probes first selected in the selection step and secondly eliminated in the modelling step (Figure S4) and the fit of the concentration-response curve for the first 49 probes selected (Figure S5).

Figure S4. Typical examples of probes first selected in the selection step and secondly eliminated in the modelling step: a very noisy data set (on the left) and a data set for which the significant response was observed only at the highest tested concentration (on the right).

Figure S5. Fit of the concentration-response curve for the first 49 probes selected (ordered by decreasing adjusted p-values). Fitted curves are reported in red against the observed response with replicates represented in open circles and means of replicates at each dose represented by solid circles.

S5) BMD DERIVATION

This part exemplifies how the control level influences the value of the derived BMD-xfold (Figure S6) and illustrates the calculation of the BMD on a biphasic model (Figure S7).

Figure S6. Illustration of BMD-10%fold. Both probes are modelled by linear CRCs with the same slope but different intercept (y_0). A situation with a low y_0 value (A) leads to a lower BMD-xfold value than a situation with high y_0 value (B), all other parameter remain equal. BMD-10%fold are highlighted by blue lines.

Figure S7. Illustration of situations where the BMD-1SD is found before the model extremum (on the left) and after the model extremum (on the right). BMD-1SD are highlighted by blue lines.

S6) CUMULATIVE DISTRIBUTION OF PROBE SENSITIVITIES PER TYPOLOGY

Presentation of one of the graphical output of the DRomics tool based on the BMD values of all the probes selected by the previous steps of the workflow.

Figure S8. Distribution of the BMD-zSD values (with $z = 1$) of each probe associated specifically to each typology of curves (typology defined in the legend of Figure 2).

S7) ILLUSTRATION OF TYPES OF DISCORDANCES IN THE REPEATABILITY STUDY

The following figure gives examples of rare probes for which a great discordance was observed between both replicates.

Figure S9. Examples of discordances between results for replicated probes.

S8) COMPARISON OF DROMICS AND BMDEXPRESS RESULTS

BMDEExpress is often used to model dose-response curves for omics data and to derivate BMD values. Therefore, we compared DRomics and BMDEExpress results on the same data set. We especially compared their ability to describe observed responses (using AIC values), BMD values and their repeatability. For that purpose, we ran BMDEExpress on a subset of 1814 probes (= 2*907), corresponding to 907 probes that were replicated and both selected using an FDR value of 0.001. For this set of samples, we used BMDEExpress for the modelling and BMD calculation step. A value of a BMR of 1 SD was used in order to obtain BDM values comparable to DRomics BMD-1SD values. As BMDEExpress is far more time consuming than DRomics, it is necessary using BMDEExpress to properly define options to optimize the calculation on the used computer. Using a Toshiba Portege laptop (Intel Core i7 with 4 cores, 2.5 GHz, 8GB RAM, Windows 7 pro) we fixed the number of threads to 16 (four times the number of available cores on the computer, as recommended in the online tutorial) and kept the model execution time out at its default value of 600 seconds (it corresponds to the maximal time the software can run a model for an individual probe). Using those parameters, the run of BMDEExpress on the subset of data took around two hours while it took around one minute using the DRomics package with the parallel computation implemented in the modelling step.

BMDEExpress was used with its default choice of proposed models: linear, Hill, power, exponential and second and third order polynomial models. BMDEExpress and DRomics provided the AIC value for each fitted model and the best AIC value (AIC value of the chosen model) for each CRC. As AIC values are calculated up to a constant, those AIC values were put on the same scale by equalling AIC values of the linear model given by both tools. We can see on Figure S10 that if best AIC values are rather similar for responses characterized by DRomics as monotonic (“inc” or “dec” DRomics trend), a great number of responses characterized by DRomics as biphasic (“U” or “bell” DRomics trend) are better fitted by DRomics, with a smaller AIC value. For 4.43% (resp. 0.52%) of the probes, the best model proposed by BMDEExpress revealed a higher (resp. lower) AIC than the one proposed by DRomics (absolute difference in AIC greater than 10). The mean differences of AIC values (BMDEExpress – Dromics) is of 0.955, with a great heterogeneity due to trend of responses: the models chosen by BMDEExpress reveal slightly lower AICs than by DRomics for monotonic responses (mean difference in AIC of - 0.38) but higher AICs for biphasic responses (mean difference in AIC of 3.09).

Figure S10. Scatter plot of AIC values of the best model chosen by DRomics (x-axis) and BMDEExpress (y-axis), with the color of each point coding for the trend of the CRC as characterized by DRomics.

Figure S11 corresponds to the scatter plot of BMD values estimated by DRomics (x-axis) and BMDExpress (y-axis). We can see on this plot that the tools gave well correlated values for monotonic CRCs, but not for biphasic responses, for which DRomics tends to give smaller BMD values. It seems that BMDExpress, which only proposes second and third polynomial models as non-monotonic models, has some difficulties to describe biphasic CRCs. DRomics made the choice of a biphasic model 6.4 times more than BMDExpress on this subset of data. This difficulty has a clear consequence on the BMD distribution (Figure S12) as BMDExpress may overestimates BMD values for biphasic CRCs.

Figure S11. Scatter plot of the BMD-1SD values estimated by DRomics (x-axis) and BMDExpress (y-axis), with the color of each point coding for the trend of the CRC as characterized by DRomics.

Figure S12. Distribution of the BMD-1SD values as estimated by DRomics (left) and by BMDEExpress (right).

Concerning the repeatability of the results obtained per probe, the method described in part “Repeatability of the results” in the main manuscript was also applied to BMDEExpress on the subset of data. The repeatability of BMDEExpress was globally lower than the one of DRomics, based on values of root mean square error (RMSE: root mean squared differences between BMD-1SD values estimated for both replicates of each probe) of 0.882 for DRomics and 1.215 for BMDEExpress. DRomics gave a slightly higher RMSE for biphasic responses (1.079) than for monotonic responses (0.733) while BMDEExpress gave less repeatable results for probes with a biphasic response (respective RMSE values of 1.803 and 0.615). This last result confirms the difficulty to give a relevant and repeatable estimation of the BMD value for biphasic responses using BMDEExpress.

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